

DIAMAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF ORGANO-METALLIC COMPOUNDS.
PART I. ANTIMONY COMPOUNDS

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The diamagnetic susceptibilities of organo-antimony compounds, R_3Sb , and their dihalides, R_3SbX_2 , have been determined by a modified form of Gouy's method. The results show that the susceptibility of antimony atom, deduced from trivalent compounds, is higher than the value deduced from pentavalent compounds. The difference in the susceptibility of tri- and pentavalent antimony has been explained on the basis of the difference in the structure of these compounds. The theoretically calculated values of $\chi_{Sb^{III}}$ and $\chi_{Sb^{V}}$ by Slater's and Angus' methods have been compared with the observed values for tri- and penta-valent Sb atom.

The present investigation deals with a study of the diamagnetic susceptibility of a series of organo-antimony compounds of the type R_3Sb and their dihalides, R_3SbX_2 . It appears from the literature that only a few organo-metallic compounds of antimony have been studied by Pascal (*Compt. rend.*, 1921, 173, 144, 712; 1922, 174, 437, 1698; 1922, 175, 1063) who deduced therefrom the susceptibility of antimony atom.

EXPERIMENTAL

The triarylstibines R_3Sb , and their dihalides, R_3SbX_2 , were prepared by the methods, already reported in the literature. Pure chemicals were used in the preparation and the crude products obtained were purified by repeated crystallisations. The purity of the compounds was established from the melting points and the percentage metal contents found by chemical analysis. In the case of dihalides, the close agreement of the observed and the reported melting points was taken as a criterion of purity, as these compounds were found difficult to decompose.

The diamagnetic susceptibility of these compounds was determined by a modified form of Gouy's method (*ibid.*, 1889, 109, 935), and the susceptibility values were calculated by using the following equation (cf. Angus and Tilsten, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, 43, 235):

$$\chi = \frac{aF + C}{w}$$

where

$$a = \frac{2l}{H_1^2 - H_2^2}$$

and $C = V \times K_m$ (volume susceptibility of air being taken as $K_m = 0.029 \times 10^{-6}$).

The calibration of the apparatus was made by using pure benzene (free from thiophene), susceptibility value of which is accurately known to be $\chi = -0.702 \times 10^{-6}$ (cf. Angus and Hill, *ibid.*, 1943, 39, 185; Baddar, Hilal and Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1, 132).

The results of the diamagnetic susceptibility measurements are reported in Table I in which χ_s represents the specific susceptibility and χ_m , the molar susceptibility values. These values are the mean of at least three independent determinations and these have been represented in terms of -1×10^{-6} c.g.s. units.

TABLE I

No.	Compounds.	Formula.	χ_s .	χ_m .	χ_m .	χ_{Sb} .
1.	Triphenylstibine	$(C_6H_5)_3Sb$	0.5169 ± 0.004 0.56 (P)*	182.3	156.27	26.03
2.	Tri- <i>p</i> -tolylstibine	$[p-Me.C_6H_4]_3Sb$	0.5484 ± 0.003	216.6	191.85	24.75
3.	Tri- <i>m</i> -xylylstibine	$[m-Me_2C_6H_3]_3Sb$	0.5750 ± 0.003	251.1	227.43	23.67
4.	Tri- <i>p</i> -anisylstibine	$[p-OMe.C_6H_4]_3Sb$	0.5198 ± 0.003	230.1	205.68	24.42
5.	Tri- <i>p</i> -phenetylstibine	$[p-ORt.C_6H_4]_3Sb$	0.5486 ± 0.003	265.9	241.26	24.64
6.	Triphenylstibine dichloride	$(C_6H_5)_3SbCl_2$	0.5077 ± 0.003	215.1	196.47	18.63
7.	Tri- <i>p</i> -tolylstibine dichloride	$(p-Me.C_6H_4)_3SbCl_2$	0.5351 ± 0.003	249.2	232.05	17.15
8.	Tribenzylstibine dichloride	$(C_6H_5CH_2)_3SbCl_2$	0.5359 ± 0.003	249.6	232.05	17.55
9.	Triphenylstibine dibromide	$(C_6H_5)_3SbBr_2$	0.4532 ± 0.003	232.4	217.47	14.93
10.	Tri- <i>p</i> -tolylstibine dibromide	$(Me.C_6H_4)_3SbBr_2$	0.4821 ± 0.002	267.4	253.05	14.35
11.	Tri- <i>m</i> -xylylstibine dibromide	$[Me_2C_6H_3]_3SbBr_2$	0.5040 ± 0.003	300.7	288.63	12.07
12.	Triphenylstibine di-iodide	$(C_6H_5)_3SbI_2$	0.4303 ± 0.003	261.1	245.47	15.63
13.	Tri- <i>p</i> -tolylstibine di-iodide	$(Me.C_6H_4)_3SbI_2$	0.4551 ± 0.003	295.3	281.05	14.25

* Pascal, *loc. cit.*

DISCUSSION

Susceptibility of Tri- and Pentavalent Antimony Atom.—The susceptibility values of tri- and pentavalent antimony atom were deduced from the corresponding molar susceptibilities of triaryl compounds and their dihalides respectively, using Pascal's values of constituent atoms and constitutive correction constants (cf. Bhatnagar and Mathur, "Physical Principles and Applications of Magneto-chemistry, 1935, pp. 90-93). These values of $\chi_{Sb^{III}}$ and χ_{Sb^V} , deduced from the corresponding compounds, are shown in the last column of Table I.

It will be seen that the susceptibility values of tri- and pentavalent Sb atom agree well with each other, in each case; the average values of $\chi_{Sb^{III}}$ and χ_{Sb^V} found being -24.70×10^{-6} and -15.50×10^{-6} , respectively. It is obvious that these values of tri- and pentavalent antimony atoms are inclusive of the effects of C—Sb and Sb—halogen, as the case may be. The difference in the values for $\chi_{Sb^{III}}$ and χ_{Sb^V}

appears to be due to the difference in the structure of these two types of compounds. The triarylstibines are probably pyramidal like many trivalent antimony compounds, such as, antimony trichloride, tribromide and tri-iodide (Sidgwick and Powell, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1940, **176A**, 153). The Raman spectra of trimethylstibine (Rosenbium *et al.*, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1940, **8**, 366) and the dipole moment of triphenylstibine (Bergmann and Schutz, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **B19**, 401) also favour the pyramidal structure for these compounds. The addition of two halogen atoms to the triaryl-stibine changes the covalency of antimony from three to five and the resulting structure is a trigonal bipyramid, as established from the physical properties of the dihalides. The crystal structure of only trimethylstibine dihalides appears to have been investigated so far (Wells, *Z. Krist.*, 1938, **99**, 367). The results indicate that this compound has a trigonal bipyramidal structure with two halogen atoms in the polar position and at a distance from the central antimony atom, intermediate between that required for electrovalent and covalent bonds. Triphenylstibine dichloride (Jensen, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1943, **280**, 257) has been found to have a zero dipole moment, as is to be expected from the trigonal bipyramid, and linking between central atom and halogen atom appears to be strongly polar in this compound. All these evidences indicate that antimony in R_3SbX_2 is pentavalent as opposed to trivalent antimony in R_3Sb and that antimony has a greater positive charge in the dihalides than in the triaryl-stibines. This positive charge arises from the strongly polar character of Sb—halogen bonds. It is obvious therefore that as a consequence of the greater positive charge on the antimony in dihalides, χ_{Sb} value would be smaller in these compounds than in the case of triaryl compounds.

Kido (*Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1932, **21**, 869) had made an interesting observation in the susceptibility values of atoms which showed more than one valency. He found that the observed difference in the susceptibility of atoms like P, As, Cl in trivalent and pentavalent states was of the order of 8-10 units. The observed difference in the susceptibility of antimony in tri- and pentavalent states is about 9 units, which is in agreement with the observation of Kido.

Comparison of Observed Values of χ_{Sb} with Theoretically Calculated Values.—The following table shows the theoretically calculated values of χ_{Sb}^{3+} and χ_{Sb}^{5+} due to Slater (*Phys. Rev.*, 1930, **36**, 57) and Angus (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1932, **136A**, 569) along with the observed values for $\chi_{Sb^{III}}$ and Sb^V .

TABLE II

 χ_{Sb} values.

	Observed.	Calculated.	
		Slater.	Angus.
Trivalent	24.70	30.60	30.45
Pentavalent	15.50	20.07	19.93

It is seen that the theoretical values, calculated by Slater's and Angus' methods, are both higher by 5-6 units than the observed values in each case. In the triaryl-

stibines, the link between Sb and C will be essentially covalent, although it may have a certain ionic character. From the difference in the electronegativities of Sb and C, the ionic character of this link is estimated to be about 15%. The departure of the theoretically calculated $\chi_{\text{Sb}^{3+}}$ values from the value deduced from trivalent compounds may be due to the formation of Sb—C bonds. Similarly, the observed difference between the calculated value of $\chi_{\text{Sb}^{5+}}$ and the value deduced from pentavalent compounds may be attributed to the bond effects due to Sb—C and Sb—halogen bonds.

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